

**MEMORY GLEANING AS STYLE AND INITIATING OF CRAFT:
IN IBEZUTE’S REDISCOVERING MY MISSION**

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Abstract

Reading is a process of acquiring memory of a literary tradition and a psychological positioning of self. Gleaning from memory is a stylistic presentation of materials of memory through the structure of art. This study explores memory gleaning as style and initiating of craft in the autobiography of Ibezute’s *Rediscovering My Mission*. Through the application of trauma theory, memory and style as a concept, this paper observes that gleaning is a process of autobiographical narrative in Ibezute’s *Rediscovering My Mission* and is mediated through the craft of internal structure and sequencing of autobiographical memories. This study further notes that the Nigerian Civil War referent and enables the writer’s creativity in *Rediscovering My Mission*. This study submits that memory piling, via the framework of reading the Nigerian Civil War narratives, awakens the writer’s creativity and induces his memory in other narratives far away from the sites of his hurt into other creative literature.

Keywords: Memory, Autobiography, Gleaning, Style, Trauma, And Nigerian Civil War.

Résumé

La lecture est un processus d'acquisition de mémoire d'une tradition littéraire et d'un positionnement psychologique de soi. Le glanage de la mémoire est une représentation stylistique des matériaux de la mémoire à travers la structure artistique. Cette étude explore le glanage de la mémoire en tant que style d'initiation à la créativité dans l'autobiographie d'Ibezute intitulé *Rediscovering My Mission*. Grâce à la théorie du traumatisme, de la mémoire et du style comme concept, cet article observe que le glanage de la mémoire comme processus de récit autobiographique dans l'autobiographie d'Ibezute passe par la créativité de la structure interne et du séquençage des souvenirs autobiographiques. Cette étude note également que la référence à la guerre civile nigériane s'ouvre à la créativité de l'écrivain dans sa mission à se découvrir. Cette étude remarque que l'accumulation de la mémoire à travers le cadre de la lecture des récits de la guerre civile nigériane, a éveillé la créativité de l'écrivain et a induit sa mémoire dans d'autres récits lointains des sites de sa blessure vers d'autres créations littéraires.

Mots-clés : Mémoire, autobiographie, glanage, style, traumatisme et guerre civile nigériano-biafraise.

Introduction

Most Nigerian literary works are constantly shaped by either experienced trauma or inherited ones in the memories of the writers. This existence of traumatic memories finds expression within the narrative framework of art. This is so in the sense that as Cathy Caruth observes, "...traumatic neurosis" emerges as the unwitting reenactment of an event that one cannot simply leave behind' (2). These traumatic memories either take the form of inherited trauma of refutation of colonialism as seem in Achebe's *Things Fall Apart* and Adichie's *Half of a Yellow Sun* or an experienced trauma as highlighted in Achebe's *There was a Country*, Soyinka's *The Man Dies* and Ken Saro-Wiwa's *A Month and A Day* which chronicle traumatic memories at different levels. Traumatic memories have been part of the narrative structure of most African writings including poetry as it is reminiscent of Ochia Ofeimun's *The New Broom*, Nnimmo Bassey's *We thought it was oil but it was blood*, Remi Raji's *Web of Remembrance* and Tanure Ojaide's *The Tale of the Harmattan*. The art "...thus represents traumatic experience not only as the enigma of a human agent's repeated and unknowing acts but also as the enigma of the otherness of human voices that cry out from the wound, a voice that witnesses a truth..." (3). The above mentioned writers are witnesses to the collective subjection of their people first by colonialism and later by internal colonialism occasioned by military rule and democracy. Ron Eyerman et al are of the view that, "...suffering...does not exist simply as material

networks. They must be imagined into being” (xii). The writers imagined the realities of their times into various narrative structures. Chukwuma Ibezute continues from this premise of imagining of the civil war suffering of himself and his people through gleaning from traumatic memories like other Nigerian writers to focus his art within a historical frame. In consonant with Ron Eyerman et al submission; “To transform individual suffering into collective trauma is cultural work. It requires speeches, rituals, marches, meetings, plays, movies and storytelling of all kinds. Carrier groups tie their material and ideal interest to a particular script about who did what and to whom and how society must respond if a new collective identity is to be sustained” (xiii). This law in respect to transferring individual memories has already occurred as was observed by individual using the individual memory to highlight the effect of the collective memory of the Nigerian Civil War on the Igbos of the Eastern region. Chukwuma Ibezute is one of the writers using individual memory of trauma to highlight the effect of the Nigerian Civil War. Van Der Kolk and Mcfarlane note that; “... traumatic experiences can alter people’s psychological, biological and social equilibrium, to such a degree that the memory of one particular event comes to taint all other experiences, spoiling the appreciation of the present” (4). There is an allusion to the writer’s traumatic experience in his books *Prison Memoirs of Gerald Williams* and *Tempters and Traitors* as narrative fillers without actually dwelling on his traumatic experiences, as it is in reminiscence of *Rediscovering My Decision*. Literary critics and scholars over the years have interrogated the works of Ibezute but none has focused on autobiographical trauma as a creative style and memory gleaning in *Rediscovering my Mission*. *The Perspective on Chukwuma Ibezute’s Writings* edited by Solomon Awuzie provides an extensive engagement on the works of Ibezute but none of the seventeen essays dwell on the creativity of traumatic memory that finds expression in the autobiographical narrative of *Rediscovering My Mission*. As a result of the lack of critical appraisal of the role of traumatic memory in the composition of Ibezute’s *Rediscovering My Mission*, this research which is titled “memory gleaning as style and initiating of craft in the autobiography of Ibezute’s *Rediscovering My Mission*” fills in the critic gap of traumatic autobiographical memory as pollinating nexus for creative writing. Jeffery A. Kottler in the book *Divine Madness* is of the view that traumatic experience can necessitate the production of creative writing and *Divine Madness* to a large extent through presentation and interrogation of some writers’ personal life illustrates the place of trauma in creative writing. In making a case for traumatic memories’ contribution to creativity, Kottler submits that; “...of the most intriguing paradoxes, that great creative achievements can occur within the disordered, tortured minds of the mentally afflicted. In many cases, it is precisely the gifted person’s pain, not to mention a rather unusual view of the world, that leads to innovation...” (ix). The

foregoing illustrates the productive nature of trauma and how some writers glean from the site of trauma for their autobiographical composition. Caruth clarifying the working of trauma notes that; "...trauma is not locatable in the simple violent in an individual's past, but rather in the way that its very unassimilated nature-the way it was precisely not known in the first instance- returns to haunt the survivor later on" (4). Most African Literary works are continuously gleaning from traumatic memory in such a way that the output becomes unique on its own. All forms of art are products of pruning from a close pool of human realities that are focused in history and imagined in human memories. This may have prompted Edet Essien's assertion that the dynamic nature of society calls for equally dynamic artists (99). This is conditioned by the artistic perception of realities, which are modified through the frameworks of society, belief, intention, language and exposure. Memory and history gleaning is a powerful storehouse for the creative writer who constantly interacts with these factors through the framework of art to inform and entertain his perceived audience. Creative writing, in form of imagined writings and autobiography, as it is illustrated in Ibezute's *Rediscovering My Mission*, is a form of literary gleaning from the "farmland" of memory and history through the process of pruning as what gives birth to creative art. Berntsen and Rubin are of the opinion that sensory organs are functional in organizing autobiographical memory (11). Ibezute's experience, which was occasioned by the Nigerian Civil War, affects his development as a writer and how he wields the sword of creativity in his art. Ibezute, in his *Rediscovering My Mission*, implicates the role of memory on how his art is built. He uses the integrative memory that thrives on lessons derived in an individual's search for meaning. However, there is the presence of use of non-integrative memory, which is just the presentation of reality the way it is without "forcing" the reader to infer meaning through the writer's point of view. Highlighting the creative writer's use of integrative memory within the framework of his narrative, the autobiographer observes that:

In a bid not to leave this persistent question without making efforts to look for a suitable answer, I began an in-depth analysis of my past and characters I had encountered in the course of my ventures and efforts to discover the treasures God had for me in this wonderful and beautiful planet earth, full of joys and sorrows. Nevertheless, for one to engage in an arduous task as this, one requires courage and skill and needs to go down memory lane to exhume the facts relating to the topic one has at hand (iv).

*Ibezute's *Rediscovering My Mission* is a self-portrait through memory gleaned of a writer with the psychological strength to "exhume" his memories that continue to implicate his art and the doctrine of his creativity. Through sequencing of gleaned memories, Ibezute accounts for his trauma and memory amidst the framework of art. He goes further to establish the doctrine on which his autobiographical narrative will proceed, as it is reminiscent of most of his literary works. In establishing the doctrine of his autobiographical narrative, he observes that, "...I reminded myself that every writer has a burden. Besides the pain associated with writing, a writer should write to educate mankind and reshape society, which is why Edet Essien informs that the efficacy and contributions of the arts to human existence, defies quantification (*Predestinasi* ... 27). While doing this, the writer must be blunt, fair and sincere to himself and his fellow citizens" (iv). The autobiographical writer, as a necessity of the style of autobiographical narrative, must be honest and blunt first to himself and his society in handling memories that have historical links to the collective memories in the society. Ibezute fits into writers who construct the collective memory from individual point of view. Volker Heins and Andreas Langnohl affirm the foregoing thus; "...cultural trauma is socially constructed through narrative and other forms of representation" (5). Ibezute personalizes cultural memory in his composition of collective trauma in his autobiography. The autobiographical memory is a continuous one that influences the writer's sequencing of his material as material of creativity. Soljana Cili and Lusia Stopia observe that; 'Fortunately or unfortunately, the past does not stay in the past. It shapes our personality, colors our view of ourselves and the world around us, and affects our emotion and how we behave or interact with our environment' (14). The past has greater influence in the autobiographical narrative and it is the same in Ibezute's *Rediscovering My Mission*. Style is used in this study to indicate how the writer gleans his memory in such a way that collective ethnic and national memory are personalized in the sequencing of self as an extension of the collective. Soljana Cili and Lusia Stopia, commenting on memory as style in autobiographical narrative, note that:

The development of the life story is facilitated by the life story schema, a mental structure that represents individuals' organization of their personal history and serves as "an interface between AM and the self.... This schema is thought to be used during autobiographical reasoning, a form of meaning making which involves individuals interpreting their experiences and memories in a highly subjective way and linking them to each other and to changing or enduring aspects of themselves (74).

This subjective process of memory as mentioned above implicates the existence of memory based on individual personal history and their changing experiences in the society. This is why Soljana Cili and Lusia Stopia suggest that age, culture, psychological well-being and processing affect how an individual responds to memory in the process of autobiographical writing (142-142). Age affects the writer's cognitive experience either to reconcile his memory with the present or to hold onto his scars. Consequently, style is memory patterning of lexical and grammatical items in a text that contributes to meaning. M.H. Abrams and Geoffrey Galt Harpham define style as:

...the manner of linguistic expression in prose or verse- as speaker or writers say whatever it is that they say. The style specific to a particular work or writer, or else distinctive of a type of writing, has been analyzed in such terms as the rhetorical situation and aim...the characteristic diction, or choice of words; the type of sentence structure and syntax; and the density and kinds of figure language" (349).

Consequently, memory gleaning and the choice of language which are resident in the personalized use of personal pronouns, fictional names that appear in negative context, become a form of style not restricted to the mentioned above in *Rediscovering My Mission*. Ibezute corroborates the foregoing thus: "The book is my portrait, although with a touch of fiction. I have put the story down as the events happened. It is a literary piece in three volumes. It is to make the book a classical novel and for some meaningful reasons, I choose to use fictitious names for some characters and places that I considered necessary" (v). What the autobiographer appears to be referring to above is the continuous "fictionalizing" of personal memory in an attempt to sequence personal memory into the autobiographical structure. This state of mind is corroborated by Martin A. Conway and Laura Jobson who inform that, "The nature of an individual is defined by autobiographical memories unique to that person. Memories, however, may also be shared across individuals who have experienced the same or similar events" (54). This is in line with Gloria Eme Worugji and Uwem Affiah's (2006) argument in their paper "Maltreatment, Greed, and Self-Centeredness..." (39) on their discussion of Myke Van Gram's experiences and past memories. This is the case with Ibezute's *Rediscovering My Mission* in the sense that there are both individual and shared memories of the Nigerian Civil War and the stigmatization of Biafra war survivors. As Ron Eyerman notes in *Cultural Trauma: Slavery and the Formation of African American Identity*, emphasis was made on the idea of trauma theory by Cathy Caruth that it is not the experience itself that produces traumatic effect, but rather the remembrance of

it” (3). Ibezute’s autobiographical narrative of *Rediscovering My Mission* is a traumatic remembrance within the framework of art. Silvia Pellicer Ortin in interrogating autobiographical narrative of trauma is of the opinion that the traumatic autobiographical narrative mainly is to expose different hidden traumas (74).

Memory Gleaning as Style in Ibezute’s *Rediscovering My Mission*

An individual’s total experience in life, which is stored in the memory, becomes an element in the encoding processes of autobiographical narratives. James M. Bebko, in writing about memory, submits that, “Memory skills are centrally involved in wide variety of cognitive activities, from simple daily skills...” (1). Since style is memory patterning imposing certain structures in the process of recalling autobiographical elements in a literary text and what is sequenced through gleaning of such memory, memory plays an important role in Ibezute’s narrative style. Ibezute’s traumatic narrative within the autobiographical framework is tied to the trauma of his people affirming the submission of Caruth that; “...one’s own trauma is tied up with the trauma of another...”(8). Ibezute’s style is mediated by the dictate of autobiographical composition in the usage of real names, the use of personal pronouns and the attempt to present certain collective facts that are products of historical memory of trauma within the context of Nigerian Biafran Civil War. Style exists within the framework of stylistics and stylistics scholars have continuously explored the relationship between style and stylistics, which have been grouped closely. Paul Simpson describes stylistics as “a method of textual interpretation in which primacy of place is assigned to language. The reason why language is so important to stylisticians is because the various forms, patterns and levels that constitute linguistic structure are important indices of the function of the text” (1). What the foregoing illustrates is that the pattern in the interpretation of stylistics is the concept of style. Simpson, in accounting for “Style as Choice”, notes that; “The experiential function is an important marker of style, especially the style of narrative discourse, because it emphasizes the concept of style as choice” (22). What seems to be implicated in the foregoing is that traumatic memory is an experiential function which authorial style gleans into for the purpose of appropriating itself as experiential description of what transpires in the mind as soon as events occur and after their passage become the function of memory. Nina Norgaard et-al see stylistics as the study of style which emphasizes how meaning is created through language in literature as well as in other types of text (1). Such meaning is extended to include the concept of traumatic memory gleaning and sequencing of narrative within *Rediscovering My Mission* as style distinctive to the referenced text and autobiographical narrative. The

autobiographical narrator within the framework of *Rediscovering My Mission* is no longer straightforward experience and reference to the site of trauma in the sense that the autobiography dictates the narrative structure, literary skills, and choices, which affect the traumatic memory gleaning. Bettina Fischer-Starcke in conceptualizing “Stylistic” defines “Stylistics” as “...the linguistic analysis of literary texts” (1). Consequently, traumatic memory becomes a linguistic subject in the study of autobiography and memory patterning and remembering becomes a style in the analysis of autobiography, as it is reminiscent of *Rediscovering My Mission*. Matthew Arnold defining style submits that “Style is the man” emphasizing that the DNA of memory becomes a definition of style, which is nurtured over the years, and this also corroborates Simpson’s concept of experiential function. Book One of *Rediscovering My Mission* opens with memory of “My Boyhood Days” and the heathen environment. Through the use of the personal pronoun, “My”, the autobiographer observes that:

A long time ago, during my boyhood days in the village, I woke up one bright morning and went and stood on the last row of the long steps of the high-base burnt-brick bungalow in which we lived. There were clucks of chicken searching for food. The front space of the compound where I used to play with other infants friends had plenty of sandy soil. Two orange trees stood some distance away from the two sides of the building (2).

The text begins with a recall of childhood memory and a conceptualization of such memory within physical environment implicated in the flora and fauna of his society. The autobiographer refers to his mother calling him “Francis Nnaa because it was believed that Francis was a reincarnation of her father” (5). Apart from the environment, cultural collective memory comes into play within the structure of the work. Ibezute engages his cultural memory, which is collective and personal to him to the extent of various cultural beliefs such as reincarnation, the nature of selecting students for school and the author’s commencement of formal education in 1963. Ibezute keeps reminiscing and sequencing his memory through flashbacks to his childhood, gradually revealing his details growing up as a boy. Bessel A. Van Der Kolk, in accounting for the nature of memory, observes that:

...memory is simply not something concrete, definite, and reproducible, like a video recording that can be retrieved at will. It is instead more ephemeral, ever-shifting in shape and meaning. Memory is not a discrete phenomenon, a fixed

construction, cemented permanently onto a stone foundation, rather, it is more like a fragile house of lands, perched preciously upon the shifting sand of time, at the mercy of interpretation and confabulation...(47).

Memory is not static since age affects the ability of the brain to compute memory such as recollected in the autobiography. The age of the writer and social realities within the society obviously affect his childhood memory in his process of sequencing his experiences and weaving them into pattern in his autobiography. Simpson considers style as experiential and such is the case in *Rediscovering My Mission*, where experiential memory of Ibezute as backed by his cultural background and education is an indicated extension of the writer's personal self. Van Der Kolk corroborated the foregoing thus; "Memory is a continued reconstruction more akin to the wayward, wildly unpredictable..." (47). This is observed in the author's ability to remember some teachers who were kind to him while ignoring those who seemed cruel to him. Mary Ruder, affirming the concept of memory as style, in the attempt to link memory with language, states that: "Working memory provides a platform for language processing by keeping information in mind and integrating it with new information during discourse as well as a platform learning..."(3). Ruder, in her paper "Working Memory for Linguistic and Non-linguistic Manual Gestures: Evidence, Theory and Application", insists on the role of memory in ordering the linguistic structures of style, She corroborates Arnold's submission that "style is the man" since cultural practices and other social norms which are elements of memory and experienced by the individual become influencers of linguistic patterning of the psychological choices which are accounted for in the written alphabets and other lexical choices within Ibezute's autobiographical narrative. The working memory of a writer influences his linguistic choices and this is clearly seen in Ibezute's *Rediscovering My Mission* in imitative voice gleaning at different points of his development. The foregoing is reflected in the struggle the author passes through to be admitted into primary school and his Nigeria Civil War experience that is selective memory gleaning which is referent to his past in an attempt to link the future, thus, affirming Caruth's submission that the future, which ought to be a continuous conversation of the past, becomes discontinued (14). The impact therefore is a disruption in the linking process of the past to the future, which the author slightly achieved. The autobiographer, chronicling his experience about his existence, also comments on the Nigerian Civil War, which are collective memories and have had significant impacts on his people. He submits that:

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On Tuesday, Eke, 30th May 1967, spontaneous joy overtook Abakaliki town and in fact, according to radio reports, all the town and cities in Eastern Nigeria. Earlier on, I had witnessed for the first time, demonstration taking place day in day out. The people of the countryside, civil servants, University undergraduates, College students, and businessmen carried placards and marched peacefully on the streets of Abakaliki Township, demanding the declaration of Eastern Nigeria as an independent nation (40).

The sequencing of the writer's memory is featured in the collective memory and in this; the writer is interested in the immediate action that leads to the war which impacts him directly. Unlike other writers like Adewale Ademoyega in *Why We Struck*, Alexander A. Madiebo in *The Nigerian Revolution and the Biafran War*, Achebe in *There was a Country*, Akachi Adimora Ezeigbo in *Rose and Bullets* who did gradual chronicling of the war, Ibezute did not pay attention to the immediate and remote causes of the civil war but sequenced his memories in such a way that one could see the effects of the war. His individual memory overshadows the collective memory. He notes that "...the recent development not only tampered with, but jeopardized the course of the journey of my destiny and forced me to change direction" (41). The foregoing implicates the concept of traumatic memory within Ibezute's autobiographer narrative. What the writer did was to look for how his future is slowed down as a result of the Federal Government's declaration of war against the independent nation of Biafra that is a referent to the Civil War. The war declaration disrupts the writer's education, however, he did not dwell much on the civil war experience. The writer is rather nostalgic of his childhood relationship with his brother, Chris, who was in business with his father, and his father's attempt to distribute his wealth before his death. The issues of the war were footnotes in the reflection of the writer's father's personality and the kind of family they exist in (42-49). The autobiographer seems to account for the desperation of individual as a result of the memories of trauma to the extent they do all within their powers to be rich. The autobiographer through portrayal of some of his peoples' sudden riches, affirms the peoples' resolves to make it in Nigeria even when the state had attempted to "destroy" them through redistribution of wealth. They did everything both legitimate and illegitimate to attempt material wealth as resisting certain federal classification. He observes that:

After the civil war, people returned to town and witnessed much changes in social life. In spite of the fact that the people

who lived in the war-affected areas during the war returned empty and poor, it did not take long when excess flamboyant and rascally life returned in greater magnitude than it was. Whether it was because of how the people felt at the peak of the civil war.... It was memorable that when some people remembered the property and wealth they left behind in the cities and towns only to face hunger at the peak of the war, they swore that if the war should ever end, they would always eat, be satisfied and have their earnings in their stomach and not to save money in the banks where it could be left again in the face of disturbance (108-9).

The war created a certain mindset and memories in the survivals to the extent that the sense of loss drove away all forms of morality from them as the war survivors struggled to become wealthy in the aftermath of the war. The battered people resolved not to deposit their wealth with the Nigerian government's financial institutions. The autobiographer traces trauma as influential agent in other peoples' conditions while presenting a semblance unaffected by the same civil war; apparently suppressing his own memory and the lingering effect on his development as a human and most importantly as a writer. The autobiographer implicates his trauma in reference to the cultural site of his peoples' traumatic experiences in a way that it seems he has suddenly forgotten his own traumatic experience. Caruth notes; "The historical power of the trauma is not just that the experience is repeated after its forgetting, but that it is only through forgetting that it is first experienced at all" (17). Ibezute through forgetting experience his trauma. The autobiographer informs us that the war destroyed the fabric of the Igbo society and made a lot of its citizens desperate for survival because that seemed to be the intention of the Nigerian government (110-150). Ibezute, in *Rediscovering My Mission*, follows Soljana Cili and Lusia Stopia's submission on autobiographical memory thus:

There are four main types of coherence that individuals try to accomplish as they construct their life story: temporal, causal, thematic, and cultural.... Temporal coherence involves ensuring that the experiences incorporated in the life story are organized in a specific (often chronological) sequence. Causal coherence involves ensuring that experiences are linked to each other and to self-characteristics in terms of cause and effect relationships. Thematic coherence involves linking experience or life elements which seem to share common themes in terms of content or the goals that individuals were

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trying to reach in the experience such as agency (e.g., power, autonomy, achievement) and communion (e.g., love, intimacy, caring). Finally, cultural coherence is achieved by ensuring that one's life story follows the template of the normative life course in one's culture... (74).

Autobiography is a cultural production in the sense that one's society shapes the autobiographer's perception of reality and memory, as the writer is associated with it. The shaping of memory of the writer is seen in *Rediscovering My Mission* when the writer makes allusions to his being named after his grandfather. Temporal coherence strives on the concept of sequencing event within the coherence art structure and the use of flashback as a recall mechanism within the work. In Ibezute's *Rediscovering My Mission* his personal experiences are linked in terms of cause and effect, in his father relocating from the village to Abakaliki town sometime in late 1957 and later fleeing to the village following the outbreak of the civil war. The unfolding war forced him to abandon his formal education and engage himself in learning various trades. He later found a career path in writing and publishing. *Rediscovering my Mission* also makes use of thematic coherence which emphasizes the effects of war and the determination of the self to become great irrespective of the challenges imposed on him by the circumstance of birth and society. The four concepts, which Soljana Cili and Lusia Stopia mention as coherence elements and link the complete work of autobiography as a single narrative of fragmented experiences, implicates our concept of style in this paper in respect to memory sequencing as conscious choice of linguistic presentation in written autobiography.

Initiating of Craft in Ibezute's *Rediscovering My Mission*

The creative spirit is a wandering one in different occupations and actions, which clusters experiences and ensures the writer's reflection stead. In the search of perceived destiny in various learning of trade in Ngwa Road Aba (160-168), after serving for a while, the writer went in search of a shop to start his own trade and later decided to relocate to Benin (169-178). After several failed attempts at business, the writer moved on in search of his dream to become a successful writer. The autobiographer notes that; "The journey in search of my mission was a tedious one. While on this journey, I met different calibers of men and women. Some wished me well and some wished me evil" (315). They, in search of what he refers to as destiny, face different situations that he classifies based on the balance of those who wish him good and others who wish him bad. In the foregoing, Ibezute makes use of both integrative and non-integrative memories in

fashioning his *Rediscovering My Mission*. He uses integrative memory in narrating lessons he learnt from his interactions with others during his trade venture as well as his dealings with his village people in Benin City which almost wrecked him. However, the writer appeared at each critical moment to be pulled back from the brink by certain benevolent forces he describes as destiny in his autobiographical narrative. He observes that:

...I couldn't tell why I kept having a vision that I would be great. This vision kept repeating itself in my consciousness that at a sense I began to wonder if I'm crazy. I understood clearly that I was educationally handicapped to rise to prominence in governmental or academic circle. I did also understand that I did not possess the lion's heart of some modern day business men which helps many commit crimes in order to acquire wealth... (315).

The autobiographer seems to introduce the concept of greatness to extend acquaintance with wealth or academics. He is haunted by a certain longing which seems to take the tag of greatness as a manifesting form in his memory. The creative spirit haunts him to the extent that he had to admit that:

I kept wondering until hardship and difficulties forced me into writing. Even if I fail to make money as a novelist and publisher, I have made an indelible name. This is my joy. Honestly, before any involvement in writing, I adored literary creativity and it is my conviction that whether rich or poor; novelists, playwrights and poets are great men and women (316).

Failure to become a success and achieve social status in his immediate environment motivates the artist to keep on searching for his unique identity. Hardship, for him, becomes an initiating factor into craft that motivates the writer to discover his art. As he notes:

It occurred to me to write down my life experiences, which I began, I could not even write up to two chapters and nothing was forthcoming. Instead, some stories I heard during my boyhood days came into my mind and when I began to put them down, the idea kept flowing from my brain. I created and reshaped the story to be a reading material. This was how I delved into writing fiction. (316).

The writer started his art after being conditioned by his memory to create internal stories that had become part of his own experience. What the writer assumes as other stories he heard could in reality be stories that had become part of his own experience. The Civil War stopped the writer from furthering his education like many Igbos after the war. Bessel A. Van Der Kolk reviewing this sort of trauma affirms that; "...trauma is imprinted in the body, and that in order to heal, one needs to create a sheltered trance state from which one can safely observe the horrific past" (19). Ibezute marks his horrific past by writing other stories that are not related to the war. These stories create a distance for him to heal and reading of his works that were motivated by the war enables him to confront his fears. The writer goes further to account for the processes of initiating his craft thus; "I need no elaboration here that I did not go back to school after the Civil War and while in business in Benin City" (316). The writer, like the collective memory of the society, continually emphasized that he did not further his education after the war and this affected the reception of his works by some persons in the society. However, the author's failed expectations and his dreams that were shattered by the outbreak of war traumatized him to the extent that he took a break from reading. Van Der Kolk seems to corroborate the foregoing thus: "All these "shockers" to the organism can alter a person's biological, psychological, and social equilibrium to such a degree that the memory of one particular event comes to taunt and dominate all other experiences, spoiling an appreciation of the present moment "(36). The civil war experience was a dominant experience, which the author avoided in most of his creativity, finding expression in other forms of composition. Ibezute corroborated the above when he states that:

I remember one day I had spelt a word wrongly and Cyril who was a bookshop operator and more conversant with reading, corrected me. I only told myself that the level of my academic brilliance had reduced considerably and that was all. I was not keen on reading. Even when one of my boys hawked novels and books using a locally fabricated truck, I did not even for one day go into one of the novels, let alone reading it. The first set of books which attracted my interest include Alexander Madiebo's *Nigerian Revolution and the Biafran War*, Ben Gbuile *Nigeria's Five Majors*, Ademoyega's *Why We Struck*, and Oyewole's *Reluctant Rebel*. In fact, I read many books on the civil war (317).

The autobiographer did not read other materials because he was traumatized by the civil war in which his memory sequencing did not dwell on. However, encountering his experiences in other autobiographical material about the war

motivated his reading that seemed to have died as a result of the war and he found relief in the materials that were collective experiences of him with that of other writers. It is symbolic to note that reading civil war autobiographies contributed to his rekindled interest in reading a form of referent literarily far from the site of trauma. After making peace with his past through the reading of civil war experiences, the writer progressed to reading other materials. Mary Chamberlin and Paul Thompson in their submission of autobiography note:

Any life story, whether a written autobiography or an oral testimony, is shaped not only by the reworking of experience through memory and re-evaluation, but also by art. Any communication has to use shared conventions, not only of language itself but also the more complex expectations of “genre” of the forms expected with a given context and type of communication (i).

The association of memories enables the writer to reshape his own experience. Memory reconciliation, through the eyes of other writers, enabled Ibezute to be able to move beyond his pain and start reading other materials as he alludes to below;

...when Newswatch magazine was launched. I began to buy every new edition of the magazine. I became “addicted” to it that my vendor-customer always reserved my copy for me. From early 1985, magazines and Newspaper became part of my routine. I later became addicted to reading. I now began to buy Fredrick Forsyth’s works, Pacesetters novels and Heinemann’s African Writers Series. Gradually, on my own, I began to observe the differences in the language of the newspaper, magazines and novels I have mentioned. Before I knew what I was into, I had established a library in my sitting room. I began to love reading materials as I had loved classical music – the class of Jim Reeves, George Jones, Kenny Rogers, Don Williams, Linda Ronadsth, the Pioneers. The Bob Marley and Fela Anikulapo Kuti for their revolutionary instincts... (317).

All the books, magazines and newspapers that Ibezute read were subtle parts of the initiating stage of his creative craft. Reading became part of the formal education process he missed out on as he became informed like other formally educated artists in his society about contemporary issues in his locality. Ibezute credits this commencement stage thus:

...I took reading Bible like a school homework. Unknown to me, every phrase and every word I came across while reading all books were building and piling up in my brain and when I began to write, English language began to flow freely. Seeing what was happening, I developed interest and spared time to study words and phrases. My natural gift in those primary school years came into play. It did not take long, when plots of different fictional works began to build up in my mind, I became more eager to study and learn. I interacted with graduates, mostly experts in English and Literature (318).

Ibezute's exposure to literary works and other written texts awoke his creativity as a writer and initiated his craft into the models of most of the texts he had studied and read in light of the concept of Plato's creed that art is an imitation of life. Ibezute further associated with those who studied English and Literature in higher institution so as to acquaint himself with normative conventions of speech and writing. He stated that; "...my innate writing was helped by my involvement in wide reading, which climaxed into private study of literature" (332). The foregoing is indicative of how autobiographical memory is fashioned in relation to other literary materials and in the author's organic society. Vickroy Laurie affirms that, "literary and imaginative approaches to trauma provide a necessary supplement to historical and psychological studies" (221). This is so in the sense that literary and imaginative autobiographical presentation of trauma provides temporary respite for the writer and allows the autobiographer to reimagine through a unique narrative structure of storytelling.

Conclusion

From the interrogation of Ibezute's *Rediscovering My Mission*, this study submits that *Rediscovering my Mission* is a product of traumatic memory which come alive through an attempt to forget or make reference to trauma far from the site of its occurrence. *Rediscovering My Mission* is autobiographical writing that is crafted through the sequencing of memory and adopting various memory structures in passing the writer's intended message. In this, the writer's culture, age, psychological state and his thought process become a residue of style. He incorporates integrative and non-integrative memory in putting his message across. Through the exploration of his work, we can see that memory confronting and memory absorbing leads to initiating of craft as it is clearly highlighted in *Rediscovering of My Mission*.

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